

**DIGITAL INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES: DEVELOPMENT, FEATURES AND
PROSPECTS FOR IMPLEMENTATION INTO THE DOMESTIC EDUCATION
SYSTEM**

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Abstract. *This article outlines the importance of innovative activities in education, since it can ensure the transformation of all existing types of practices. Considering the transition to a global information society and the development of knowledge, the adequacy of education to the socio-economic needs of the present and future can only be said if its modernization is based not only on organizational innovations, but also on changes in the content and technologies of personnel training.*

Keywords: *education, personnel, digitalization, innovation, technology, pedagogy, practice, educational environment, approaches, innovations.*

Аннотация. *Ушбу мақолада таълимда инновацион фойдалигини муҳимлиги ҳамда унинг амалиётдаги барча турлариини такомиллаштиришдаги аҳамияти асосланган. Глобаллашган ахборот жамиятига ва билимларни такомиллаштиришга ўтишни ҳисобга олган ҳолда таълимнинг мавжуд ижтимоий-иқтисодий шарт-шароитларга адекватлиги тўғрисида гапирганда нафақат таълимнинг янгиликлар балки унинг мазмуни ҳамда кадрлар тайёрлашда қўлланиладиган таълим технологияларига эътибор қараши ниҳоятда муҳим.*

Калим сузлар: *таълим, кадрлар, рақамлаштириш, инновация, технология, педагогика, амалиёт, таълим муҳити, ёнлашув, янгиликлар.*

Аннотация. *В настоящей статье обозначена важность инновационной деятельности в образовании, так как она способна обеспечивать преобразование всех существующих типов практик. Учитывая переход к глобальному информативному обществу и становлению знаний, об адекватности образования социально-экономическим потребностям настоящего и будущего можно говорить лишь в том случае, если его модернизация будет основываться не только на организационных нововведениях, но и на изменениях в содержании и технологиях подготовки кадров.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, кадры, цифровизация, инновации, технологии, педагогика, практика, образовательная среда, подходы, нововведения.*

Currently, more and more attention is paid to innovation in the educational process. Innovation in teaching, as well as in production, first of all means innovation, updating, changing existing pedagogical technologies used in educational and educational processes. Innovations, or innovations, are characteristic of many professional human activities and therefore, naturally, become the subject of study, analysis and implementation.

The goals of innovation in education are: ensuring a high level of intellectual, personal and spiritual development of the student; creating conditions for him to master the skills of a scientific style of thinking; teaching the methodology of innovation in the socio-economic and professional spheres; formation of sustainable interest in the chosen profession, as well as in the innovative initiative.

The main criterion for innovation is novelty, which is equally relevant to both the assessment of scientific pedagogical research and advanced pedagogical experience. Therefore,

for a teacher who wants to get involved in the innovation process, it is very important to determine what the essence of the proposed new is, what is the level of novelty.

Pedagogical innovation is the process of developing, implementing, testing and evaluating innovations in the field of education that help effectively achieve set goals. Innovation and goals are closely related to each other: the educational process changes over time, the labor market makes new demands on future employees, and training is transformed, adjusted to new goals, the achievement of which requires new pedagogical methods, techniques and methods.

Innovations in education help achieve the following goals: humanization, democratization of the educational process; intensification of students' cognitive activity; increasing the efficiency of organizing educational and educational work.

New approaches that are actively being introduced into the pedagogical process help to realize the set goals. Pedagogical innovations are based on two key approaches:

A student-centered approach implies focusing the educational process on the personality of each student. Modern pedagogy must take into account the unique experience and character of each student, develop his individuality and talents. The implementation of this approach includes reliance on the principles of choice (students can choose the areas they want to pursue), trust (lack of authoritarian pressure from teachers), creativity and success, subjectivity, individuality.

The competency-based approach is new for the national school. He focuses on the result of learning, and the result is not a body of knowledge, but a set of skills, the student's ability to solve problems, conflicts, and act in different situations.

At the same time, modern pedagogy offers such innovative pedagogical technologies as, for example, project work, gaming technologies, distance learning, interactive technologies and portfolios.

For example, Project work is a type of activity that helps develop students' creative abilities and develop their teamwork skills. The purpose of the projects is to update and use in practice, expand and deepen the acquired knowledge. Work on a project can take place individually, in pairs or in microgroups; it involves solving a problem and searching for optimal solutions. This innovation forms and develops complex thinking, the ability to analyze, establish connections and create new ideas, and see a holistic picture of the world.

Gaming technologies perform several functions: entertainment, therapeutic, diagnostic, social. During the game, students engage in free developmental activities, receiving pleasure and effect not only from the result, but also from the process.

In the educational process, the game is used as an element of a broader technology, part of a lesson or extracurricular activity. A pedagogical game has a clearly formulated goal, which is presented in the form of a game task; all participants in the game are subject to pre-prepared and voiced rules.

Distance learning is an innovation that is actively being introduced into the modern educational process. Courses are created on specially designed platforms, which include lecture series, assignments, and a schedule of face-to-face consultations with teaching. Students organize their time independently and discipline themselves for self-study.

Interactive educational technologies are one of the types of innovative teaching technologies. They are focused on broad interaction between students both with the teacher and with each other in the process of acquiring professional knowledge and skills. Interactive technologies are implemented through the holding of seminars, debates, problem lectures, discussions in schools, where students can present their thoughts and learn to argue their opinions.

The main distinctive feature of interactive educational technologies is the development of personal initiative, the development in students of a desire to acquire new knowledge and skills, which underlies competency-based and student-oriented approaches to learning.

The portfolio helps to assess the dynamics of learning outcomes. With its help you can visualize educational achievements and discoveries. This innovation is implemented through the following methods of accumulating information: electronic portfolios, “folders of achievements,” “growth diaries.” They record all developments and projects, collect materials that confirm participation in projects, discussions, and the results of creative activity.

It should be said that pedagogical innovation is also an innovation in the field of pedagogy, a targeted progressive change that introduces stable elements (innovations) into the educational environment that improve the characteristics of both its individual components and the educational system itself as a whole.

One of the effective ways to solve problems of improving the quality of education is the informatization of education. Improvements in technical means of communication have led to significant progress in information exchange. The emergence of new information technologies associated with the development of computer tools and telecommunications networks has made it possible to create a qualitatively new information and educational environment as the basis for the development and improvement of the education system.

Innovative learning technologies should be considered as a tool with the help of which a new educational paradigm can be put into practice. The main goal of innovative educational technologies is to prepare a person for life in an ever-changing world. The essence of such training is the orientation of the educational process towards human potential and their implementation.

Education should develop mechanisms of innovation, find creative ways to solve vital problems, and contribute to the transformation of creativity into the norm and form of human existence. Developing the ability to motivate actions, independently navigate the information received, the formation of creative, unconventional thinking, and the development of children through the maximum disclosure of their natural abilities, using the latest achievements of science and practice, are the main goals of innovative activity.

To develop and improve the innovation process, a deep analysis of all the problems of educational technologies is necessary, summarizing the vast experience of pedagogical innovations, original schools and innovating teachers.

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